

RESEARCH ARTICLE

GLOBALIZATION AND STATE SOVEREIGNTY

***Mohd Ashraf Ganaie and Shafiq Mohiuddin**

Department of political science, Vikram University Ujjain (M.P)

ARTICLE INFO

Article History:

Received 08th February, 2016
Received in revised form
05th March, 2016
Accepted 01st April, 2016
Published online 10th May, 2016

Key words:

Conventional wisdom,
Globalization, State sovereignty,
Multinational, Internet,
Aggressive powers, Global media.

Copyright © 2016, Mohd Ashraf Ganaie and Shafiq Mohiuddin. This is an open access article distributed under the Creative Commons Attribution License, which permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided the original work is properly cited.

Citation: Mohd Ashraf Ganaie and Shafiq Mohiuddin, 2016. "Globalization and State Sovereignty", *International Journal of Current Research*, 8, (05), 30960-30961.

ABSTRACT

Globalization Without any iota of doubt had contributed to bring lot of changes and reductions to the scope of State Sovereign Powers. There had being numerous threats to the state sovereignty of which special can be made of Global financial flows, multinational Corporations, global media empires and the internet. The World War Second had changed everything drastically and most of the sovereign state deliberately and consciously limited their rights. The reasons behind such deliberate acts on the part of such sovereign states was that they had the intention to gain quite real advantages by becoming the members of regional and inter regional unions. Globalization gave us an alarm call that the lines ahead to us are a great threat in the form of capital labour and the different inequalities which could make us pay a heavy price, If we don't listen to the call of the hour which is to limit hour aggressive power's for the betterment of our societies in general end of the world in particular. This deceleration given by the former president of the international court of justice represented the conventional wisdom about of global governance.

INTRODUCTION

This Article explains that the impact of Globalization on state sovereignty. The Globalization is the dominant force which has shaped a new era of interaction and interdependence among nations. It has many dimensions such as economic, political, military, social and cultural dimension. It creates both opportunities and costs to the nation state. Sovereignty is the most essential element of the state. Globalization contributes to the change and reduction of the scope of state sovereignty. The scope of inner sovereignty has legally narrowed to a large degree due to the international agreements including Global financial flows, activities of international Organization and Multinational Corporations, Information communication technology and issues concerning Human Rights and in connection with already formed models and traditions of states' behaviour. At the same time increasingly more states quite often give away some of their sovereign powers voluntarily for certain reason. Globalization is a process many facets of which have been subjected to a discussion by the writers belonging to a wide spectrum of theoretical and political positions. International relations scholars are interested in debates about Globalization and Governance partly because of a deeper concern about change versus continuity in the international system (Simon Dalby 2003).

**Corresponding author: Mohd Ashraf Ganaie,*
Department of political science, Vikram University Ujjain (M.P).

Says Globalization is a buzzword that has no precise definition. (Charles Kegley and Wittkopf 2006) Globalization may be described as increasing and intensified flows between countries of goods, services, capital, ideas, information and people, which produce cross- border integration of a number of economic, social and cultural activities. It creates both opportunities and costs (Guido Bertrucci and Adriana Alberi 2004:1). Sovereignty is the most essential element of the state. A sovereign state will have high levels of capacity, and external, internal and subjective autonomy.

Objectives

- To demonstrate that, by the Globalization the list of threats to state sovereignty often includes Global financial flows, Multinational Corporations,
- To determine that the Globalization Contribute the Powerful Development of Trade, Transport and The Role of International Capital, MNS etc on State Sovereignty.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The study will be conducted through secondary sources in an interdisciplinary approach. The design of the study will be exploratory in nature and the major concern of the proposed study will to evaluate the impact of globalization on national

state sovereignty. The present research work would be analytical and fact based the current work is theoretical in nature. Hence it is based on secondary sources on data. For this purpose, the reference books shall be widely consulted, the access to internet research journals, occasional papers, government reports regarding Globalization shall be assured.

Description

There have long been debates as we all know about the relationship of the individual states to the capitalists views range from those who emphasize the degree to which states are manipulated by capitalists to serve their individual and collective interests to those who emphasize the degree to which states are autonomous actors who deal with capitalists as one interest group among several or many. There has also been debate about the degree to which capitalists could escape control by the state machines, and there are many who are many who are arguing that their ability to do this has increased considerably in recent decades, with the onset of the transnational corporation and so called globalization in addition, there have long been debates about the relationship of so called sovereign state to each other views range from those who emphasize the effective sovereignty of the various states to those who are cynical about the ability of so called weak states to resist the pressures (and blandishments) of so called strong states. This debate is often kept separate from the debate about the relationship of individual states to capitalists, as though we were dealing with two different questions. It seems to be difficult however to discuss these issues intelligently without looking at them in tandem, because of the peculiar structure of the modern world system, the modern world system in existence in at least part of the globe since the sixteenth century, is a capitalist world economy. This means several things. A system is capitalist if the primary dynamic of social activity is the endless accumulation and indeed only a few are able to do so successfully. But a system is capitalist if those who do engage in such activity tend to prevail in the middle run over those who follow other dynamics. The endless accumulation of capital requires in turn the ever-increasing modification of everything and a capitalist world economy should show a continuous trend in this direction which the modern world system surely does.

Conclusion

Globalization is a sprawling concept with a wide range of definitions. We have focused on globalization's acceleration of the moment of goods and services, people, capital, and information in ways that hamper a state's ability to regulate all activity on its territory the central definition of national sovereignty. Conduct that crosses state borders gives rise to demands for international cooperation.

We argue, however, that efforts to solve globalization's effects by turning automatically to international organizations and law that take precedence over national sovereignty are premature and inconsistent with the continuing power and relevance of nation states. Rather than reject international law, or conjure forth the demise of the nation state, we propose a middle way. Popular sovereignty establishes the constitution as the authoritative mechanism for the generation and enforcement of national law within the United States.

REFERENCES

- Annan, K. A. 1999. Two concepts of sovereignty. *The Economist* 352.49-50
- Armstrong, J.A. 1982. *Nations before Nationalism*. Chapel Hill, NC; University of Carolina Press.
- Basa, K.K. 2004. Globalization and Cultural Heritage in the Third World. *Journal of the Indian Anthropological Society*, 39 (3): 227-254.
- Berger, P.L. 1986. *The Capitalist Revolution*. New York: Basic Books.
- Bhagwati, J. 2004. *In Defense of Globalization: How the New World Economy Is Helping Rich and Poor Alike*. Oxford-New York; Oxford University Press.
- Bull, H. 2003 *Beyond the States System?* In Held and McGrew 2003b:577-582
- Byazrova, J.B. 2004. Globalization and the problem of national values. *Filosofia I obschestvo* 4:62-69
- Camilleri, J.A. 1990. Rethinking Sovereignty in a Shrinking Fragmented World. In Walker, R.B.J, and Mendlovitz, S.H. (eds), *Contending Sovereignties: Redefining Political Community*.(13-44). Boulder, CO: Lynne Rienner
- Chopra, J., and Weiss, T.G. 1992. Sovereignty is No Longer Sacrosanct: Codifying Humanitarian Intervention. *Ethics and International Affairs*.6:95-117.
- Daniels, R. and Alarie, B. 2003 *State Regulatory Competition and the Threat to Corporate Governance*. In Courchene and Savoie 2003a:165-184.
- Eisenstad, Sh. N. 2010. Contemporary Globalization and New Civilization Formations. *Journal of Globalization Studies*, 2(1):3-1
- Garner, J.W. 1925. Limitations of National Sovereignty in International Relations. *The American Political Science Review*, 19 (1):1-24
- Gay, W.C. 2010. Globalization, the problem of war, and Normative Issues. *Journal of Globalization Studies*.1 (1):141-149
- Grinin, L. E. 2004. Globalization and Problems on National Sovereignty. In Materials of 'The Round table', devoted to the day of philosophy UNESCO, November, 18, 2004.(pp.39-47), Bishkek: Dana. In Russian
